

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Ageing@Work web portal

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Executive Summary

The present document is a report that was prepared as deliverable “D8.2: Ageing@Work web portal” of the Ageing@Work project (Grant Agreement No. 826299), funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 (H2020), and presents the online dissemination channels of Ageing@Work as they were created and developed within the first months of the project.

In particular, Ageing@Work has established a wide variety of communication channels (official web portal, social media, etc.) in order to disseminate the project’s main objectives, activities, events, achievements and results. In this direction, the deliverable is organised in four main sections. It starts by introducing the current report and proceeds by describing the project’s web portal and key social media, before ultimately concluding with the deductions resulting from the elaboration of the report.

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1. Introduction

This report constitutes a detailed description of the Ageing@Work web portal and presents the functionalities of the webpage together with the social media accounts that have been established for the needs of the project. The web portal along with the established social media channels of the project will be optimised and enhanced with essential dissemination material, which is expected to serve as a multiplier of the project’s main ambitions and objectives.

With that in mind, the following table outlines the key online communication channels utilized in the framework of the Ageing@Work project.

Table 1. Ageing@Work’s main online communication channels

Channel	URL
The Ageing@Work web portal	https://ageingatwork-project.eu/
The Ageing@Work account on Twitter	https://twitter.com/AgeingWorkproj1
The Ageing@Work page on Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Ageingatwork-project-434374127300138/
The Ageing@Work on LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ageing-work-project/
The Ageing@Work channel on YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCJsxLGgNFnLi0

All the above-mentioned online communication channels are expected to contribute greatly to the dissemination of the project results and outcomes. In this initial stage, the communication channels were selected in order to cover the majority of online social media and are expected to be active during the entire timeline of the project and after its completion.

With that in mind, “D8.2: Ageing@Work web portal” was organized in the following chapters:

- **Chapter 1 – Introduction** states a brief description of Ageing@Work’s online presence and introduces its web portal together with the accounts of social media accounts that have been assigned to the project.
- **Chapter 2 – The Ageing@Work web portal** describes Ageing@Work’s web portal in order to support all the necessary horizontal activities of the project.
- **Chapter 3 – Ageing@Work Presence on Social Media** describes the channels to be employed for efficient dissemination, awareness raising and communication through online social media.
- **Chapter 4 – Conclusions** details the deductions resulting from the development of the deliverable.

2. The Ageing@Work web portal

The Ageing@Work web portal is publicly available at <https://ageingatwork-project.eu/> and it was designed during the early stages of the project, in order to support all the necessary horizontal activities of the project. The Ageing@Work web portal is based on a common layout that guarantees easy browsing through the site's web pages. More specifically the layout is presented in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 and consists of:

- The **Header** section, which contains the project logo and its full name, as well as the **Main Navigation Menu**, which facilitates the fast browsing between the different sections of the web portal.
- The **Main Content Area**, the main part of every page, presenting the users' information requested.
- The **Sidebar**, containing a twitter feed of the Ageing@Work's latest tweets, a newsletter subscription link and the latest project news.
- The **Footer** containing the social media links, the structure of the web portal (sitemap) and the information about the project's funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 framework.

Figure 1. Ageing@Work's web portal layout (top)

Figure 2. Ageing@Work's web portal layout (center)

Figure 3. Ageing@Work's web portal layout (bottom)

The content and structure of the Ageing@Work web portal was organized and designed to have the presentation of the project, both in terms of goals and background, as well as the presentation of news related to Ageing@Work's work. Site visits, statistics and other information on visitor's views (e.g. number of pages per visit, time on site, most viewed pages, etc.) will be measured using Google Analytics. The following list presents the main sections of the page, which are further analyzed in the following subsections:

- **Home:** The homepage holds a header menu (Figure 4) as well as presents a slideshow, a short summary of Ageing@Work, the latest project news and a tweets feed of Ageing@Work's latest

tweets. The main purpose of this page is to summarize the project goals and its current state in a glance.

- **Project:** This section aims to present all the detailed information related to the project. More specifically, the subsections are presented below.
 - **Concept & Approach:** This section presents Ageing@Work’s overall concept in a nutshell.
 - **Objectives:** The cornerstone objectives that will define the outcomes of the project are summarized in this section.
 - **Consortium:** The purpose of this section is to present the project’s consortium.
 - **Related projects:** This section presents several related projects along with the links to their individual web portals
- **Results**
 - **Public Deliverables:** List of public deliverables together with download links for each one after its successful completion.
 - **Dissemination material:** List of the promotional material (leaflet, poster, etc.) developed for the communication and dissemination of the project.
- **News & Events:**
 - **News:** This blog contains a list of news related to the goals of the project and publication of project results. This section will be used to share experiences and outcomes between the partners and the community of web portal users.
 - **Newsletter:** In this section, the web portal visitors can see all the project newsletters and are presented with the possibility to subscribe and receive future editions through mail when they are available.
- **Contact us:**
 - **Contact:** In this section, the web portal visitors are able to provide feedback regarding a part of the project or even the functionalities of the web portal. The contact information of the Ageing@Work project coordinator [Dr. Konstantinos Votis](#) is also available in this section.
 - **Privacy and Cookie Policy:** This section contains the Privacy and Cookie Policy of the Ageing@Work web portal.

Figure 4. Ageing@Work’s web portal menu

THE AGEING@WORK CONCEPT IN A NUTSHELL

The overall concept underpinning Ageing@Work starts from the urgent need to help ageing workers of the modern industries to maintain productivity and workability, while achieving a balance between work and personal life, in the context of active and healthy ageing.

Having identified the changes in human abilities that appear with age and typically affect workability, Ageing@Work will follow an interdisciplinary approach in developing novel advanced ICT solutions for adaptive smart working and living environments in order to effectively meet those needs.

The system that we are going to develop will be demonstrated in the context of use case scenarios in real life environments and with the participation of actual users from the targeted user group. We will provide two use case demonstrators, by the end of the project. One use case involves workers in mining industrial site to test Ageing@Work holistic approach in outdoors conditions and a second use case concerns industrial workplace.

Figure 5. Concept and approach web page

OBJECTIVES OF THE AGEING@WORK PROJECT

Ageing@Work will research and develop a platform of ICT tools, which on one hand, will help tailoring the workplace to the evolving needs and specificities of the ageing workers, both in terms of ergonomics and in terms of work processes and task assignments and on the other, will support the ageing worker's active and healthy ageing at work and at home. To support workability, the platform will include physical and mental health support ICT tools, as well as telepresence and productivity enhancement tools, based on advanced AI, AR, VR and virtual assistant technologies, and with particular emphasis on flexible management of work, along with quality of life support.

The objectives of the project are:

OBJECTIVE 1: ENABLE EXTENSIVE PERSONALIZATION CAPABILITIES TO THE AGEING@WORK SUPPORTIVE APPROACH

The project starts with the research and development of the virtual worker model and the virtual workplace model, as the basis for improving the design of the working and living environments of ageing workers.

OBJECTIVE 2: DESIGN A NOVEL UNOBTRUSIVE WORKER ACTIVITY AND BEHAVIOUR MONITORING FRAMEWORK, COUPLING WORK, ON THE MOVE AND HOME-BASED TRACKING ELEMENTS

Figure 6. The Objectives web page

PARTNERS

CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS (CERTH)

CERTH
CENTRE
FOR RESEARCH
& TECHNOLOGY
HELLAS

Website:
<https://www.certh.gr>

SIEMENS AG

SIEMENS
Ingenuity for life

Website:
<https://www.siemens.com/global/en/home.html>

UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID

POLITÉCNICA

Website:
<http://www.upm.es/>

Figure 7. The Consortium web page

RELATED PROJECTS

FACTORY2FIT

Factory2Fit - Worker-centred solutions for factories of the future

Website:
<https://factory2fit.eu/>

ACROSSING

ACROSSING

ACROSSING – Advanced TeChnologies and PlatfoRm foR Smarter Assisted Living

Website:
<http://www.acrossing-itn.eu/>

Figure 8. The Related Projects web page

PROJECT NEWS

FEB
25
2019

AGEING@WORK KICK-OFF MEETING IN THESSALONIKI!

AGEING@WORK project was kicked-off in Thessaloniki, Greece, during a two-day meeting attended by representatives of the thirteen consortium partners.

Figure 9. The News web page

AGEING@WORK NEWSLETTER

There is currently no content classified with this term.

SUBSCRIBE HERE

Fill in your personal information here in order to subscribe to the Ageing@Work Project's Newsletter

Email Address *

First Name

Last Name

SUBMIT

Figure 10. The Newsletter web page

<p>CONTACT INFO</p> <p>Dr. Konstantinos Votis Researcher C</p> <p>Building A - Office 2.8 Information Technologies Institute Centre of Research & Technology - Hellas 6th km Xarilaou - Thessaloniki, 57001, Thessaloniki, Greece Tel: +30 2311 257722 Fax: +30 2310 474128 Email: kvotis@iti.gr</p>	<p>CONTACT</p> <p>Your name *</p> <input type="text"/> <p>Your e-mail address *</p> <input type="text"/> <p>Subject *</p> <input type="text"/> <p>Message *</p> <input type="text"/> <p>CAPTCHA</p> <p>This question is for testing whether or not you are a human visitor and to prevent automated spam submissions.</p> <p>Math question *</p> <p>12 + 1 =</p> <input type="text"/> <p>Solve this simple math problem and enter the result. E.g. for 1+3, enter 4.</p>
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Figure 11. The Contact us web page

PRIVACY AND COOKIE POLICY

Introduction

This Privacy Policy applies to the AGEINGATWORK website and governs personal information and collection usage by the website only. AGEINGATWORK website is committed to being transparent and to ensuring your privacy is protected. By using this website, you consent to the personal information practices described in this policy.

This privacy policy is effective from 22/02/2019. We reserve the right to update or change our Privacy Policy at any time and you should check this Privacy Policy periodically.

Type of personal information that we collect

While using our site, you may share with us on a voluntary basis your name and/or email address through AGEINGATWORK contact page and subscription to our newsletter tool.

Use of personal information that we collect

We may use this information to contact you with newsletters, to disseminate information about AGEINGATWORK activities and results or to promote information from other projects or third parties which we think you may find interesting.

Share of information collected

AGEINGATWORK website does not sell or lease its contact lists to third parties. AGEINGATWORK website keeps a copy of its contact list to MailChimp server (<http://mailchimp.com>), which is used for e-mail campaigns and newsletters distribution. All personal information included in this contact list is used and protected according to MailChimp Privacy Policy, Section 12.

AGEINGATWORK website may share contact personal information within the Consortium to send you email for specific dissemination purposes. All such third parties are prohibited from using your personal information except to provide dissemination to AGEINGATWORK, and they are required to maintain the confidentiality of your information.

AGEINGATWORK website will disclose your personal information, without notice, only if required to do so by law.

Figure 12. The Privacy and Cookie Policy web page

3. Ageing@Work's presence on Social Media

Based on the social networking trends, the presence of the project on major social networks and content platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube has been delivered from the early project phases. To enhance the interlinkage of the web portal with the project's social media accounts there are short-links to all project social media channels in the Ageing@Work web portal.

Figure 13. Social media links on the Ageing@Work web portal

A quick overview of the main social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube) that have been created for disseminating the project results is presented below.

Figure 14. The Ageing@Work project on Facebook

Figure 15. The Ageing@Work project on Twitter

Figure 16. The Ageing@Work project on LinkedIn

Figure 17. The Ageing@Work project on YouTube (no content yet)

4. Conclusions

This report has presented the online presence of Ageing@Work, emphasizing on its web portal and social media accounts as part of a multi-dimensional dissemination, awareness raising and communication approach that will address all relevant target groups and raise public awareness about the solutions to be created, developed and demonstrated in the framework of Ageing@Work, with a view to paving the way for their successful rollout and uptake beyond the end of the project.